

Power and Spectral Savings in Metro-Aggregation Networks Exploiting Coherent Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract We carried out a comprehensive study based on experimental models and real-life dynamic traffic. We showed savings in ASIC power consumption up to 44% in topologies inspired by deployed networks from Telecom Italia (TIM) when moving from point-to-point to point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers. ©2024 The Author(s).

Introduction

Over the past decades, bandwidth consumption in the information and communication technology sectors has experienced exponential growth^[1]. Based on innovations such as AR/VR, 6G connectivity, 4K/8K video, AI, and the constant evolution of the Internet and computing services, researchers predict that this trend will continue^[2].

The design of network architectures is a multi-faceted challenge, becoming increasingly critical in the context of future optical networks. Although such networks must exhibit qualities of flexibility, scalability, and sustainability, current telecom infrastructures often fall short of these requirements as they are typically designed to address peak traffic. However, traffic displays a dynamic behaviour, e.g., exhibiting different peak times within a day based on applications^[3] or patterns depending on the day of the week and season.

In this context, it is beneficial to focus on optimizing energy and spectrum usage. Energy efficiency is a significant metric, as mentioned in^[1], where various strategies can be considered: replacing electrical aggregation with optical, reducing the number of transceivers, increasing flexibility such as adaptive bandwidth allocation and scalability, etc^[4]. Furthermore, spectrum optimization can lead to cost-effective strategies, potentially postponing costly fiber deployments. One of such strategies can be effectively enabling new services through network slicing with Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM)-based Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) transceivers^[4].

In this study, we demonstrate the advantages of tracking traffic profiles using coherent P2MP transceivers employing DSCM^[5]. We present a framework for a techno-economic study considering dynamic bandwidth allocation using realis-

Fig. 1: Considered network topologies. Shapes represent nodes: □-hub, ○-leaf, and ◊-transit. More details in^[6].

tic traffic profiles and metro-aggregation topologies modeled after networks from Telecom Italia (TIM). We also utilize a simulation tool^[6] based on experimental measurements with DSCM-based P2MP transceivers. The primary objectives of this work are to showcase the operational savings in the Application-specific Integrated Circuits (ASIC) by adapting the data rate to the traffic profile and to highlight the flexibility in network utilization enabled by the lower granularity embedded in DSCM-based P2MP coherent transceivers.

Network topologies

In our study, we have considered network topologies inspired by TIM's real network (Fig. 1). Each of these topology examples possesses special characteristics and particular challenges that differentiate them from the rest.

In these networks, leaf nodes are in charge of electrically aggregating the traffic from the connected users. As previously covered, future traffic

demands and growth forecasts dictate the design and eventually hardware deployment for an operator^[7]. Within the context of this analysis, we refer to the highest bandwidth demand that the network will experience from its users at some point in time as ‘peak traffic’. Table 1 summarizes these conditions for the networks in Fig. 1.

Network ID	Peak traffic (sublink 1; sublink 2, ... N)
Network 1	10.7; 165.2; 498.1; 88.1 / (762.1) [Gbit/s]
Network 2	308.8; 118.5 / (427.3) [Gbit/s]
Network 3	255.0; 583.3 / (838.3) [Gbit/s]
Network 4	186.4; 120.0; 284.1 / (590.5) [Gbit/s]

Tab. 1: Peak traffic requirements per sublink. In parentheses, the overall peak traffic.

Dynamic traffic behavior

To capture the effect that dynamic traffic conditions have in the operation of the DSCM-powered pluggable transceivers in the network, TIM provided a set of traffic profiles for fixed connectivity services, which describe the data rate demands in Table 1 according to the time of day. Both traffic profiles exhibit a similar behavior: low throughput late at night until the very early morning, and a ramp up for the working hours (Large businesses) and evening activities (Consumer/Home office).

Fig. 2: Time-dependent traffic profiles provided by TIM.

By calculating the dynamic traffic requirements of a network, we can estimate both the peak traffic conditions as well as the amount of resources that would be required to cope with these demands. In this regard, Fig. 3 illustrates the relation between actual traffic conditions (represented by a dashed line) and potential operating conditions of the hardware (stacked bars) corresponding to Fig. 1 (a). At the 15-hour timestamp, the users’ data rate demands are at a peak level; therefore, we use this maximum value to dimension the hardware units that are needed. Based on the traffic of the individual leaf nodes and the granularity offered by the 25 Gbit/s subcarriers, 12×100 Gbit/s transceivers would have to be commissioned to effectively satisfy the traffic demands, since some leaf nodes require multiple units. Using traditional transceivers, where a single carrier delivers the full 100G bandwidth, the overall capacity of the leaf nodes cannot be adap-

Fig. 3: Time-dependent traffic estimation (dashed line) compared to the overall capacity of the leaf nodes in Network 1 using traditional single-carrier 100G transceivers vs 100G (4×25 G) DSCM transceivers.

tively adjusted, i.e. has to be fixed at 1.2 Tbit/s, despite the total requirements at the network nodes being much lower, especially during those low-traffic periods at night.

A DSCM-based approach, on the other hand, offers the flexibility of adapting to the dynamic traffic conditions by adjusting the operating conditions of the optical transceivers (i.e., turning on/off the 25 Gbit/s subcarriers and corresponding processing elements of the module).

Fig. 4: Normalized power consumption of the ASIC as a function of type of capacity and number of Digital Subcarriers (DSCs)

Relative power consumption of the network

The possibility of scaling down the operation of transceivers enabled by DSCM offers advantages not only in terms of spectral flexibility, but also in terms of power consumption due to the reduced number of processes and computations required when operating the hardware. Fig. 4 shows the normalized measured power consumed by the ASIC for different capacity configurations (100G and 400G using 4 DSCs and 16 DSCs, respectively) as a function of the number of active or in-service DSCs.

Here, the total power of the ASIC consists of functional blocks that can be switched-off depending on the number of DSCs. However, since some of those functional blocks are shared (e.g. ADC/DAC, and the channels’ MUX/DEMUX), the total power of the ASIC will not tend to zero when all DSCs are switched off. Based on Fig. 3, we can determine the required operating settings of the pluggable transceivers to optimally ad-

Fig. 5: (a) Normalized power consumption in Network 1 as a function of the time of day. (b) ASIC operative savings for the four considered networks and different level of aggregation.

dress dynamic traffic conditions at the leaf nodes. Then, by considering traffic aggregation at the hub node^[6] (i.e., sharing a hub transceiver among multiple sublinks), we can determine the corresponding type of hardware and their capacity that will be deployed at the hub node. Aided by Fig. 4, we can in turn calculate the overall consumption of the pluggables' ASICs in the network. The overall consumption of the pluggable transceivers in the network is calculated by the following expression: $P_{\text{Network}}(t) = P_{\text{Hub}}(t) + \sum_{i=1}^M P_{\text{Leaf-}i}(t)$, where M is the total number of pluggables at the leaf nodes in the network and t denotes time.

The results of our power consumption analysis, shown in Fig. 5 (a) can be summarized in three different overarching network operating conditions: (1) Point-to-Point (P2P) with $M \times (4 \times 25\text{G})$ DSCM pluggables using all the available capacity (P2P-Full), (2) P2P with $M \times (4 \times 25\text{G})$ DSCM pluggables using the necessary DSCs to meet the traffic demand (P2P-Scaled), and (3) P2MP using P2P with $M \times (4 \times 25\text{G})$ DSCM pluggables at the leaf nodes as well as $(16 \times 25\text{G})$ high-speed DSCM pluggables at the hub node according to the level of aggregation (P2MP-AggLevel). Note that for the scenarios (1) and (2), the hub node must replicate the hardware configuration of the leaf nodes 1-to-1.

The data in Fig. 5 (a) has been normalized to the reference scenario (1), since it represents the most extreme, that is full capacity, operating conditions of the leaf nodes' hardware. Due to the lack of dynamic adaptation, the ASIC-focused power consumption remains constant. On the other hand, looking at the data corresponding to scenarios (2) and (3), it is evident that the curves' behaviour is dictated by the scaled-down operation of the pluggables according to Fig. 3. Moreover, by optically aggregating sublinks and matching them to a common source/receiver at the hub node, overall power consumption of the

pluggables' ASICs can be further improved. The reasons for this are that by using high-speed transceivers, not only do we require fewer pluggable units but also the modules are more power-efficient than multiple lower-speed ones.

Finally, Fig. 5 (b) summarizes the operative savings of the transceivers' ASICs depending on the operating conditions of the network compared to 100G DSCM pluggable modules, configured to work at full capacity. While our results demonstrate that there is a benefit in adjusting the settings of the DSCM-powered transceivers to match the traffic demands, a larger benefit can be achieved by switching to a P2MP communication paradigm for the metro-aggregation network, substituting multiple low-speed transceiver modules for fewer units with more capacity at the hub nodes. This trend can be seen in all networks shown in Fig. 1: By deploying networks that exploit DSCM in P2MP schemes, savings larger than 25% in terms of the overall power consumption of the ASICs can be realized. Furthermore, by increasing the level of aggregation, savings as high as 40%–44% could be achieved in some scenarios. However there is a limit to this; since the hardware configuration depends on peak traffic and how the sublinks are connected to the high-speed hub transceivers, there might be aggregation levels that require a similar number of components and operating conditions. For this reason, ultimately, savings in power are going to be mainly dependent on the provisioning of a network and an effective traffic allocation scheme.

Conclusions

We have highlighted the potential of digital sub-carrier multiplexing (DSCM) in adapting to dynamic traffic conditions. Our findings demonstrate significant energy savings of up to 44% in ASIC power consumption compared to traditional methods when adopting a point-to-multipoint communication approach.

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